

1 **PI3K inhibition in cancer reveals control of senescence by energy homeostasis.**

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7 We modeled chemical inhibition of PI3K in humans, like which occurs during administration of a PI3K
8 inhibitor to patients with breast cancer in the clinic, by measuring total transcription with RNA-sequencing
9 in two cellular systems (cell lines) following exposure to the small molecule inhibitor of the p110 catalytic
10 subunit of PI3K with idelalisib. We describe here existence of a novel pathway to senescence induction in
11 human cells involving the energy homeostasis function of PI3K. Senescence induction following chemical
12 inhibition of PI3K was characterized by activation of CDKN2C and CDKN3. Senescence induction
13 involving the energy homeostasis function of PI3K was independent of the function of CDK4/6 on cellular
14 proliferation as CDKN induction proceeded despite activation of both CDK4 and CDK6 in response to
15 idelalisib exposure. Chemical inhibition of PI3K may be associated with a senescence-inducing property
16 which occurs independently of cellular proliferation. Clinical interventions involving administration of a
17 PI3K inhibitor in cancer may thus likely be utilized for reintensification of therapy following loss of response
18 to chemotherapy of relapse following a previous complete response, occurring through cell
19 cycle-independent induction of senescence.
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